

Novelty driven AutoRecs Personalized Vehicle Recommendation System

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Abstract

Vehicle recommendation systems are essential in helping consumers locate the perfect car that suits their unique requirements and tastes. The state-of-the-art in vehicle recommendation systems is reviewed in this study, with an emphasis on methods that make use of vehicle attributes and user preferences. The main problems are that the consultants' staff lacks technical expertise and gives little thought to the needs of the clients. The sale of the car is their primary goal. Customers thus deal with a variety of challenges both before and after purchasing their car. This research uses machine learning technology to create a novel vehicle recommender system that uses guidance and suggestions to help clients solve this challenge. Here, we used information gathered from car sellers and users to construct a neural network model.

Keywords: *Machine learning, User Preferences, Consumers, Experience, CRS, Decision-making.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is undergoing a significant transformation at the dawn of a transformative era, driven by technological advancements that are radically changing how we think about transportation. The combination of machine learning with the automotive industry has resulted in innovative applications that aim to transform the entire car-buying experience in this era of data-driven decision-making. With a strategic use of the powerful features built within the Random Forest algorithm, this research delves deeply into the creation and application of an advanced Car Recommendation System (CRS).

The traditional car-buying process has changed, moving from straightforward dealership visits to a convoluted maze of choices. In contemporary times, buyers must navigate a vast selection of alternatives, a maze of options that necessitates a more customized and subtle approach. Acknowledging the necessity for a customized and effective resolution, the CRS becomes the central focus of this endeavor.

Through the smooth integration of user preferences, historical data, and complex vehicle specs, the CRS aims to go beyond the one-size-fits-all approach by providing customized suggestions that align with the distinct requirements and preferences of every single customer.

The need to close the current gap between consumers and the wide variety of vehicles on the market is what drives this ambitious endeavor. Given the intrinsic complexity of the car recommendation assignment, the Random Forest algorithm—which is well-known for its ability to handle a variety of datasets and produce reliable predictions—becomes crucial in tackling the problem. By means of ensemble learning, the CRS not only takes into account the individual decision trees but also cleverly leverages the collective intelligence of a "forest," guaranteeing a degree of resilience and flexibility that is essential when maneuvering through the complexities of the automotive domain.

Starting this investigation with the goal of giving consumers the newfound ability to make educated decisions while also streamlining the car-buying process is the main objective. The CRS represents a paradigm change in the way decision support systems are treated in the automotive industry by positioning itself as a useful tool for users. It represents a disruptive force that goes beyond simple utility to question accepted norms and rewrite the story of how people engage with the complex world of car choices.

This introduction marks the start of a journey into the creation, application, and careful assessment of a car recommendation system by providing the groundwork for a thorough inquiry. Redefining the dynamics of car selection in the modern market is the goal, in line with the current trends of technical innovation and customer-focused decision-making in the automotive sector.

User preferences on car attributes are used by the Random Forest technique for car selection to train a model made up of several decision trees. Recursively splitting nodes is used to create these decision trees in order to decrease impurity. Each tree casts a vote based

on the user's preference during prediction, with the majority voting to determine the outcome. With this method, the algorithm is resistant against noisy data and less prone to overfitting, and it can handle huge datasets and high dimensionality. On the other hand, it could be difficult to understand and demand more processing power. If imbalanced datasets are present, performance might also suffer.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

T. G. Thomas Et Al [01] - "Vehicle Recommendation System Design The Web uses a Hybrid Recommender Algorithm" This paper developed a web based complimentary program for vehicles. The main purpose of this function is to recommend the car according to the user model and object profile. In this paper, the proposed hybrid recommendation algorithm is used from user-to-user and interactive filtering methods aimed at generating vehicle recommendations. The user model is built with personality features, click data and browsing history.

Srivastava, A. Kumar, Et Al [02] - "Vehicle Recommendation Method Using Vengatesan K Machine Learning Algorithm". This paper studied and found that more than 90% of planned drivers regularly show that eliminating any driving pollution can control their chances and adaptability. This weight conveys the idea that it is actually improving in terms of how half of the late respondents had eliminated any driving distractions that they felt were an open car that, or in some way, lacked.

G. Prabowo Et Al [03] - "Recommendations for the Combined Filtering Program (CF)". This paper proposed a program that can help provide information about vehicles that are in line with user preferences, i.e., a recommendation system. The recommendation system requires appropriate recommendations. In this study you will focus on the problem of recommending a car selection system by creating a recommendation system using a collaborative filtering process.

Pubudu Boteju Et Al [04] – “Vehicle Recommendation System using Hybrid Recommender Algorithm and Natural Language Processing Approach”. This paper introduced a novel vehicle recommender system which helps and assist customers when it comes to vehicle buying decision. With the development of this recommender system, any user can get personalized recommendations based on general user inputs they enter to the system and giving to the system vehicle body type preferences in their natural language. The results show that multiclass neural network algorithm performs better comparing with multiclass random forest and multiclass logistics regression algorithms for collaborative and Knowledge based filtering for recommendation purposes. Also, the results depict that this Hybrid approach and Natural Language Processing based recommendation produces high quality personalised recommendations.

Hao Nan Li Qingfeng Wang Et Al [05] – “Exploring Personalised Autonomous Vehicles to Influence User Trust”. This paper proposed and examined a new approach of personalisation to make AVs more trustworthy and thereby gain higher levels of acceptance systems. The results of this research contribute to making driving safe.

Mr. Raghavendra C K Et Al [06] – “Personalized Recommendation Systems (PRES): A Comprehensive Study and Research Issues”. This paper the existing recommendation systems are designed depends up on CBF and CF techniques. The recommendation systems suffer from the problems such as changing data, lack of data, unpredictable items and changing user preferences. A good recommender system needs item data for analysis. The data are then fed to algorithms. The accuracy of the recommendations depends on volume of item and user data. One of the parameters used in building recommendation systems is users past behavior. This is not a good parameter because the trends keep changing. Another challenge to recommendation system is changing user preferences. User response to some items is diverse and unpredictable. Hence, it is difficult to make recommendations on such items.

Xinpeng Wang Et Al [07]– “A Method of Personalized Driving Decision for Smart Car Based on Deep Reinforcement Learning”. This paper a model is designed to validate the feasibility of deep reinforcement learning in the self-learning of personalized driving decisions. Driving data are collected for multiangle, multidimensional analysis. For the automatic driving task, the driving decision system is designed based on the DDPG algorithm. The environmental parameters are entered, and the driving action parameters are output. Through pretraining, the input driving parameter dimension, the determined. The mapping relationship from the sensing parameters to the motion parameters is learned to realize the self-learning of driving decisions. Considering the functional support of the simulation platform, the personalization factor is introduced and associated with the personalized indicator. A personalized driving decision model is built based on the decision-making self-learning ability. Finally, the model is trained and tested online. The advantages of the proposed method are demonstrated by comparing with traditional methods and drivers. It is possible to effectively self-learn personalized driving.

Saumya Singh, Et Al [08] – “Car Recommendation System Using Customer Reviews”. This paper proposed system could be act both as specific search tool or recommender as well as an expert car advisor or a community-based suggestion, but in the digital form. The recommendation provides a personal preference for user needs. In the proposed method, which is a combination of user-to-user and object to a collaboratively based object to recommend filtering an algorithm that works well for suggesting. The biggest problem with car databases is that they are dynamic data because it is difficult to predict the car model that will be released in their product. In addition, the performance of the proposed system can

be improved by using a real-time network that allows you to build websites and access session information. This research activity can be expanded as information-based complimentary programs using a variety of information presentations.

Muhammad Nasrun, Et Al [09] – “Recommendations for Car Selection System Using Item-Based Collaborative Filtering (CF)”. This paper proposed will focus on the problem of recommending the car selection system by building a recommendation system through an item-based Collaborative Filtering approach. This aims that recommendations are generated in accordance with user profiles and references. To calculate the accuracy of recommendations, mean absolute error (MAE) testing is used. The application of item-based Collaborative Filtering algorithm produces a recommendation system that has a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.202 and has an accuracy rate of 95.955%. The rating predictions produced by the recommendation system differ from one car to another, depending on the combined similarity value and user rating pattern in the previous car. From the satisfaction testing that has been done, obtained from 30 respondents amounting to 79.53%, respondents gave positive responses and suggestions and criticisms of the recommendation of the car using the item-based CF method, respondents also strongly supported the existence of a recommended car application.

Falah Y H Ahmed, Et Al [10] – “Enhancement of Mobile-Based Application for Vehicle Rental”. This paper proposed system develop a knowledge-based model that can be used digitally via a smartphone application to service the vehicle rental system in Malaysia called EZGO. EZGO is a website that allows consumers to look for vehicles such as cars, bikes and rental vans that can have the most satisfactory outcome and avoid the rejection of unavailable car rental by providing substitute vehicles that are close to the needs of the customer. It implemented an agile approach for the design and development of mobile apps, developed UML diagrams for the car rental system, and performed a survey of prospective customers using questionnaires. This has demonstrated how EZGO functions, and how it will contribute to the society. EZGO seeks to benefit both to the vehicle rental provider and customer.

Leyo Babu Thomas, Et Al [11] - “The Design of Web Based Car Recommendation System using Hybrid Recommender Algorithm”. This paper proposed hybrid

recommender algorithm is the combination of user-to-user and item-to-item collaborative filtering method to generate the car recommendations. The user model is designed using demographic features, click data and browsing history. Item profile is built using the various attributes of car, 40 brands of car including 224 car types are used in this work. The synthetic dataset of 300 users with 10000 sessions is used to build user model. The proposed algorithm is evaluated with 100 real time users and shows the 83% accuracy in generating recommendations.

Gayatri Khanvilkar, Et Al [12] – “Smart Recommendation System based on Product Reviews using Random Forest”. This paper proposed system compares the results of machine learning algorithms like Multinomial Naive Bayes algorithm, Logistic Regression, SVM Classifier, Decision Tree and Random Forest. These algorithms are used for sentiment analysis of reviews and in turn for product recommendation. It mainly focused on performance of Random Forest algorithm. On the basis of experimental results, random forest performed well on the dataset. It provided very promising results with accuracy of 95.03%. By using classification techniques it’s been concluded that Random forest can also provide good and competitive results and can provide better results if data splitting ratio and number of estimators are perfectly tuned. The main contribution of this work is the performance investigation of different machine learning methods while performing sentiment analysis and using sentiment polarity for recommendation.

III. CONCLUSION

In the automotive sector, car recommendation systems are invaluable since they give consumers individualized and dynamic purchasing insights. Our study shows that random forest classification algorithms are a useful tool for creating user-preference-driven car recommendation systems.

We have demonstrated through thorough testing and analysis that this method is capable of reliably predicting appropriate car alternatives and processing a wide range of user inputs. Notwithstanding its efficacy, it is imperative to recognize certain limitations. This Flask web application predicts fuel efficiency and suggests appropriate cars by using a Random Forest Regressor model to refine recommendations based on user input.

The process of buying an automobile is changing as a result of a tendency toward increasingly complex and user-centric systems brought about by technological advancements. The adaptability of the app allows it to function as a recommender as well as a search engine, and it envisions a time when digital platforms will be seamlessly integrated to provide a positive and powerful car-buying experience.

In addition to utilizing existing technology capabilities, the suggested approach paves the way for a completely transformed consumer experience in the digital real market.

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